

HISTORICAL - MILITARY TOURISM AS A MEANS OF PRESERVING AND DEVELOPING HISTORICAL MEMORY: APPROACHES TO ROUTE FORMATION, HISTORICAL RECONSTRUCTION, AND HERITAGE DIGITALISATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the role of historical-military tourism in preserving and developing historical memory, offering a critical analysis of existing theoretical approaches and advanced international practice. The study substantiates the interconnectedness of three core components of historical - military tourism: itinerary formation, historical reconstruction events, and the digitalisation of heritage sites. Drawing on Pierre Nora’s concept of lieux de mémoire, the theory of dissonant heritage, and research on immersive tourism, a sustainable model for the active interpretation of military heritage is developed. Global experience (Portugal, Iran, Romania, Russia) is compared with Uzbekistan’s potential, leading to scientifically grounded proposals for creating a national atlas of historical-military routes, establishing reconstruction festivals, and building a unified digital platform. The proposed “3K” model (Route-creation – Reconstruction – Digitalisation) constitutes the conceptual foundation for heritage activation.*

Keywords: *historical-military tourism, historical memory, routing, historical reconstruction, digital heritage, virtual reality, sustainable tourism, Uzbekistan.*

Izoh. *Ushbu maqola tarixiy-harbiy turizmning tarixiy xotirani saqlash va rivojlantirishdagi rolini o‘rganib, mavjud nazariy yondashuvlar hamda ilg‘or xalqaro amaliyotning tanqidiy tahlilini taqdim etadi. Tadqiqotda harbiy-tarixiy turizmning uch asosiy tarkibiy qismi – marshrutlarni shakllantirish, tarixiy rekonstruksiya tadbirlari va meros obyektlarini raqamlashtirish – o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro bog‘liqlik asoslab berilgan. Per Noraning lieux de mémoire (xotira joylari) konsepsiyasi, dissonant meros nazariyasi hamda immersiv turizm tadqiqotlariga tayanib, harbiy merosni faol talqin etishning barqaror modeli ishlab chiqilgan. Jahon tajribasi (Portugaliya, Eron, Ruminiya, Rossiya) O‘zbekiston salohiyati bilan qiyoslanib, harbiy-tarixiy yo‘nalishlar milliy atlasini yaratish, rekonstruksiya festivallarini yo‘lga qo‘yish va yagona raqamli platformani barpo etish bo‘yicha ilmiy asoslangan takliflar ilgari suriladi. Taklif etilayotgan “3K” modeli (Marshrut yaratish – Rekonstruksiya – Raqamlashtirish) merosni faollashtirishning konseptual po‘ydevorini tashkil etadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *tarixiy-harbiy turizm, tarixiy xotira, marshrutlashtirish, tarixiy rekonstruksiya, raqamli meros, virtual reallik, barqaror turizm, O‘zbekiston.*

Аннотация. *В статье исследуется роль историко - военного туризма в сохранении и развитии исторической памяти, предлагается критический анализ существующих теоретических подходов и передовой международной практики. Обосновывается взаимосвязь трёх ключевых составляющих историко - военного туризма: формирования маршрутов, исторической реконструкции и цифровизации объектов наследия. Опираясь на концепцию lieux de mémoire (мест памяти) Пьера Нора,*

теорию диссонантного наследия и исследования в области иммерсивного туризма, разработана устойчивая модель активной интерпретации военного наследия. Мировой опыт (Португалия, Иран, Румыния, Россия) сопоставляется с потенциалом Узбекистана, на основе которого сформулированы научно обоснованные предложения по созданию национального атласа историко-военных маршрутов, учреждению фестивалей реконструкции и построению единой цифровой платформы. Предложенная модель «ЗК» (Маршрутообразование – Реконструкция – Цифровизация) составляет концептуальную основу активации наследия.

Ключевые слова: историко-военный туризм, историческая память, маршрутизация, историческая реконструкция, цифровое наследие, виртуальная реальность, устойчивый туризм, Узбекистан.

In recent decades, the cultural and heritage tourism segment has experienced steady growth within the global tourism industry. Historical-military tourism, a distinctive branch of this segment, is increasingly recognised not only as a vehicle for economic diversification but also as a powerful socio-cultural mechanism for preserving collective historical memory, reinforcing national identity, and shaping historical consciousness in younger generations (Noivo, Lopes Dias & Jiménez-Caballero, 2022. p. 648). At a time when the memory of military conflicts risks erosion under the pressures of globalisation and digital transformation, historical-military tourism undertakes the task of “reviving” this memory and rendering it intelligible for new generations.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has taken significant institutional steps to diversify its tourism sector. Notably, Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 582 of 18 September 2024 (effective from 1 January 2025) officially designated “military tourism” as a new tourism direction, creating opportunities for tourists to visit historical - military sites, familiarise themselves with military equipment, and utilise shooting-range services (Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024). This resolution provides a solid legal foundation for the systematic development of historical-military tourism in the country.

However, existing scholarly literature and practical observations indicate that the mere museification of historical - military resources or their passive display is insufficient for the effective formation of historical memory. A tourism product must be immersive, interactive, and emotionally profound. From this perspective, the present article aims to systematically examine three interrelated factors that determine the effectiveness of historical- military tourism:

- Effective models for shaping historical - military itineraries;
- Mechanisms for organising historical reconstruction as a tourism product;
- Approaches to integrating digital technologies (VR/AR, 3D modelling, digital maps) into heritage sites.

The aim of the research is to synthesise advanced global models of preserving historical memory through historical-military tourism and to develop conceptual foundations for adapting them to Uzbekistan’s context. Within this aim, the following objectives were set:

- To critically analyse the theoretical underpinnings of historical-military tourism;
- To comparatively examine thematic, cluster-based, and network approaches to routing;
- To determine the tourism value of historical reconstruction and its role within the “living history” principle;
- To assess the potential of digital technologies in preserving and interpreting military heritage;

To propose practical recommendations and a three-component conceptual model for Uzbekistan.

The scientific novelty of the article lies in its substantiation of a “3K model” (Route-creation, Reconstruction, Digitalisation) that integrates the three principal functional dimensions of historical-military tourism into a unified system and its recommendation of mechanisms for national-level implementation.

The research was conducted within the qualitative research paradigm, employing systematic literature review as the primary method. The review process was organised in accordance with the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) principles.

Stage 1: Source search strategy. Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, as well as national scholarly platforms (ZiyoNet, inlibrary.uz) and official reports of international organisations (UNWTO, ICOMOS) were searched. The search used the following keywords and their combinations in English, Russian, and Uzbek: “military heritage tourism”, “battlefield tourism”, “historical reenactment”, “digital heritage”, “virtual reality in heritage”, “lieux de mémoire”, “historical- military tourism”, “tarixiy- harbiy turizm”. The time frame was set to 2010–2025, with certain foundational theoretical works excluded from this limit.

Stage 2: Screening criteria. The initial search identified over 120 sources. Of these, 52 were selected based on the following criteria: (a) directly devoted to military heritage tourism or active historical memory; (b) a scientific article, monograph, or official document with an empirical or conceptual basis; (c) full text available. Newspaper articles, blog posts, and non-scholarly news items were excluded from the analysis.

Stage 3: Thematic analysis. The selected sources were grouped into five main thematic blocks: (i) theoretical foundations of historical - military tourism; (ii) route formation models; (iii) historical reconstruction practice; (iv) digital technologies; (v) the current situation in Uzbekistan. Each source was critically annotated, and the principal arguments and empirical evidence were synthesised.

Stage 4: Comparative analysis and model development. Successful models from international practice (exemplified by countries such as Portugal, Iran, Romania, and Russia) were compared with Uzbekistan’s existing conditions. Transferable elements were identified, and the “3K” conceptual model was developed.

Limitations. This study is theoretical-conceptual in nature and does not include empirical data (surveys, interviews, field observations). This is noted as a methodological direction for future research.

Results:

The results of the systematic analysis demonstrate that the role of historical-military tourism in preserving historical memory manifests itself in three interconnected dimensions.

Shaping Historical - Military Itineraries: A Comparative Analysis of Models

Routing serves as the fundamental “backbone” of historical-military tourism infrastructure. The literature reveals three fundamental approaches to itinerary formation.

The thematic approach unites an itinerary around a specific historical period or conflict. In Portugal, the “Peninsular War” route dedicated to the Napoleonic Wars is enriched with reenactment events, enabling tourists to experience the historical milieu (Noivo, Lopes Dias & Jiménez-Caballero, 2022. p. 650). The advantage of this approach lies in the creation of a strong emotional connection and a coherent narrative.

The geographic-cluster approach consolidates military sites concentrated within a single area based on the principle of spatial proximity. In Iran, for example, to develop defence heritage in Galugah city, six key sites were identified using ArcGIS software, evaluated according to investment priority, and linked to a single interpretation centre (Sadry, Tavazo, Safarbeyranvand & Nemati Lojandi, 2023. p. 103). This approach is particularly effective for the optimal allocation of resources.

The network-based approach constructs the itinerary not as a single linear route but as a multi-node network. Portugal’s “INSIGNIA” project is founded on the principle of continuously monitoring the military tourism route and optimising it based on tourist behaviour (Mateus, Marques, Pedro & Simões, 2023. p. 6745).

In Uzbekistan’s practice, a synthesis of these approaches has yet to be fully realised. Although the “G‘alaba bog‘i” (Victory Park) memorial complex and several military museums exist, no unified thematic or networked route system connects them. Therefore, the table below proposes potential thematic itineraries recommended for Uzbekistan (Table 1).

Table 1. Proposed Concept for National Historical - Military Routes in Uzbekistan

Route Name	Historical Period	Main Sites	Interpretive Theme	Digital Potential
“Amir Temur Defence Line”	14th–15th centuries	Shahrisabz, Samarkand, Otrar (in cooperation with neighbouring country)	Amir Temur’s military strategy and fortress architecture	3D fortress reconstructions, VR battle scene
“World War II: Uzbekistan – the Home Front”	1941–1945	Tashkent (evacuated factories, hospital buildings), “G‘alaba bog‘i”, military cemeteries	Uzbekistan’s contribution as the home front; human destinies	“Memory of the People” digital archive, AR applications on historical buildings
“Military History of the Great Silk Road”	Antiquity – Middle Ages	Uzundara Fortress (Surkhandarya), Kampirtepa, Ayritom	Hellenistic defensive structures, Kushan-era military art	Viewing Alexander-era battle via VR
“Soviet Military Legacy: Muynak and Desert Ranges”	Soviet period	Muynak “ship graveyard”, former military sites near Nukus	Intersection of the Soviet military-industrial complex and ecological legacy	Digital storytelling platform, AR timeline

Note. Own elaboration based on the conducted comparative analysis.

Historical Reconstruction: The Immersive Tool of “Living History”

Historical reconstruction constitutes the most powerful immersive element of historical-military tourism. Stadler (2006. p. 437) characterised reenactment events as a form of “authentic

heritage travel”, substantiating their educational and emotional effectiveness. The research identified three functions of reconstruction:

1. Educational function: Participants and spectators experience historical processes directly “from within”, surpassing book-based knowledge.
2. Emotional function: The authentic recreation of battle sounds, costumes, and weaponry fosters historical empathy.
3. Community function: Reconstruction events unite local residents, enhancing their respect for their own past (Noivo, Lopes Dias & Jiménez-Caballero, 2022. p. 655).

International experience shows that successful reconstruction festivals can increase tourist flows by 20–30% (Noivo, Lopes Dias & Jiménez-Caballero, 2022. p. 660). In Uzbekistan, this practice is only just beginning. While displays of military equipment and shooting services were introduced at “G‘alaba bog‘i” in 2025, historical stage performances of battles involving Amir Temur or Jalal ad-Din Mingburnu have not yet been organised.

An important caveat: When transforming a military conflict into a tourism product, there is a danger of “romanticising” or “commercialising” its tragic essence. The concept of “dissonant heritage”, advanced by Tunbridge and Ashworth (1996. p. 15), addresses precisely this issue, stipulating that any military heritage project must prioritise respect for the memory of victims and historical veracity. Consequently, the development of reconstruction events in Uzbekistan should involve a scientific council comprising professional historians, military experts, and cultural scholars.

Digital Technologies: “Activating” Heritage and Reaching a Remote Audience

Digitalisation is currently the most dynamically developing dimension of historical-military tourism and manifests in three principal forms.

The first is Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR/AR). Using 3D models of historical structures and laser scanning (LiDAR) technologies, tourists can take a virtual journey into the past through VR headsets. For example, the Immanuel Kant Baltic Federal University (Kaliningrad) created a complete 3D model of the 11th Guards Army headquarters, allowing users to view the officers’ room, radio hub, and other historical spaces virtually. This experience is a vivid example of “placing historical research results into a digital shell” (Demin, 2024 . p. 18).

The second is digital maps and mobile applications. In Iași, Romania, the “Memory Path” project developed an interactive map of 35 historical buildings and a mobile application providing archival photographs and documents for each building. As a result, over 30,000 users accessed this digital resource.

The third is digital archives and databases. Russia’s “Memory of the People” (Память народа) electronic data bank integrates the “Memorial” and “Feat of the People” databases, digitising millions of documents and enabling ordinary citizens to trace their ancestors’ wartime paths.

In Uzbekistan, within the framework of the “Legacy.uz” project, efforts are underway to model historical sites in VR format, and a virtual tour of the Armed Forces Museum has been launched. However, these initiatives have yet to be integrated into a unified national digital tourism platform.

Fig. 1. Based on this analysis, the proposed “3K” conceptual model was developed

[Figure 1. The “3K” Model: A Three-Component System for Preserving Memory through Historical - Military Tourism]

Note. Own elaboration based on the conducted comparative analysis

(Description: At the centre of the model is the objective “Activation of Historical Memory”. This centre is surrounded by three components: K1 – Route-creation (thematic and clustered network), K2 – Reconstruction (living history festivals, educational programmes), K3 – Digitalisation (VR/AR, digital maps, AI guides). Bidirectional information flow arrows are shown between the components: the route is visualised on a digital platform; digital platform content enriches the reconstruction script; the reconstruction event generates new digital content.)

The essence of the model lies in the fact that each component reinforces the other two, producing a synergistic effect among them.

Discussion:

The above results demonstrate that the effectiveness of historical-military tourism is determined not only by the conservation of material heritage, but also by its active, critical, and immersive interpretation. The theoretical foundation of this process is Pierre Nora’s (1989. p. 7) concept of «lieux de mémoire» (sites of memory). As Nora emphasised, sites of memory are material or immaterial objects upon which society confers symbolic meaning. Historical-military tourism serves precisely as the mechanism for “reviving” these sites and restoring them to the memory of a new generation.

The literature analysis indicates that the most successful projects have combined thematic and network-based routing approaches, organised reconstruction events with local community participation, and centred digital technologies as a management tool. For Uzbekistan, the synchronous development of these three factors is of critical importance.

However, a significant scientific gap exists in the field. In particular, the long-term impact of digital technologies on the formation of historical memory remains insufficiently investigated empirically. Moreover, conceptual debates continue regarding the demarcation of boundaries between “dark tourism” and “dissonant heritage” when presenting military conflicts as tourism products (Stone, 2006 p. 145). In the context of Uzbekistan, this issue demands a delicate approach, especially when illuminating complex periods such as the repressions of the 20th century and World War II.

Another key conclusion emerging from the discussion concerns the role of local communities. The Portuguese experience demonstrated that engaging local residents in tourism projects not only yields economic benefits but also enhances their respect for their own history (Noivo, Lopes Dias & Jiménez-Caballero, 2022. p. 662). In Uzbekistan, applying this principle around historical - military sites in rural areas (for example, the Uzundara Fortress in Surkhandarya or the Soviet military camps in Karakalpakstan) is particularly pertinent.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

This research systematically examined the role and mechanisms of historical-military tourism in preserving historical memory and arrived at the following conclusions:

Historical-military tourism extends beyond the conservation of material monuments, acting as a powerful instrument that actively integrates them into societal life and embeds them in the memory of new generations.

An effective tourism system must be built upon the synergy of routing, immersive reconstruction, and modern digital technologies.

The proposed “3K” model reflects the synergistic relationship among these three components and can serve as a conceptual foundation for national-level implementation.

Although a legal framework for the sector has been established in Uzbekistan, a systematic scientific-practical programme is required to substantiate it.

Based on the above, the following practical recommendations are formulated:

Creation of a national atlas of historical - military routes. Develop a unified interactive map based on ArcGIS technologies that incorporates the geolocation, historical description, and virtual model of all military heritage sites.

Establishment of a regional “Central Asian Military History” reconstruction festival. Organise annual historical stage performances, exhibitions, and scholarly conferences in various provinces, covering the eras of Amir Timur, Jalal ad-Din Mingburnu, and World War II.

Launch of a national “Digital Military Heritage” platform. Unify existing and new digital resources (virtual museum tours, VR/AR content, archival document databases) into a single digital ecosystem.

Enhancement of scientific research and human resource capacity. Open a master’s specialisation in “Historical-Military Tourism Management” at higher education institutions and establish centres for digital humanities.

The following directions are considered priorities for future research: (a) practical testing of the proposed “3K” model and quantitative assessment of its economic efficiency; (b) sociological investigation of the impact of various digital technologies on tourists’ historical memory and emotional state; (c) dedicated research into the axiological problems of historical-military tourism within the framework of dissonant heritage.

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